

A Study on the Perception of the Youth towards Agriculture Sector- A study in the Nagaon District of Assam

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Abstract

Participation of India's youth in the agricultural sector can bring about solutions to the unemployment problems in our country. But the question is how can the youth be motivated to take up agriculture as a profession and whether this sector has enough prospect to support a respectable livelihood? In India 33.7 per cent of operational land holding belong to the to the 41-50 years age group while 33.2 per cent is within the 51-60 yrs age group. out of 100 million farmers. These group of people are reaching the age group of retirement from agriculture, but next generation does not want to engage themselves in agriculture. The study was conducted in Nagaon district in Assam state during 2023-24 to analyze the perception of farm youth towards agriculture and to enlist the problems encountered by farm youth practicing agriculture. Two hundred farm youth from 20 villages of four blocks in Nagaon district were sampled for the study. Relevant data was collected from 200 farm youth using a structured interview schedule. It was found that more than three-fourth of the farm youths (76.50%) had medium to high level of perception towards agriculture. Education, family size, land holding, family income, risk orientation, economic motivation, innovative proneness, social participation, mass media use, extension contact, extension participation, cosmopolitaness, farm scientist contact, farming commitment and training received of farm youth had positive and significant relationship with the perception towards agriculture. Nineteen independent variables selected for the study had contributed to the tune of 70.50 per cent of variation in developing better perception of farm youth towards agriculture. Lack of necessary timely inputs, lack of irrigation facilities, electricity problem, and scarcity of labor were the most important problems faced by the farm youth practicing agriculture. Provision of irrigation facility, supply of regular power, timely supply of necessary inputs and timely provision of credit were accorded the first four suggestions offered by farm youth to overcome the problems faced by them in agriculture.

Key words: Youth, Perception, Agriculture Nagaon, Unemployment

Introduction

Participation of India's youth in the agricultural sector can bring about solutions to the unemployment problems in our country. But the question is how can the youth be motivated to take up agriculture as a profession and whether this sector has enough prospect to support a respectable livelihood? In India 33.7 per cent of operational land holding belong to the to the 41-50 years age group while 33.2 per cent is within the 51-60 yrs age group. out of 100 million farmers. These group of people are reaching the age group of retirement from agriculture, but next generation does not want to engage themselves in agriculture. According to reports, farming is becoming a non-profit making venture which has affected the interest of the farming community more particularly to younger generation as the farm income is low or highly fluctuating. Youth can play an important role in transforming the agricultural sector in India. In our country about 35 per cent of the population is in the age group of 15-35 yrs, out of which 75 per cent belongs to the rural area. Apart from now a days there is ale increase in the migration of rural youth to urban areas for better livelihood opportunities.

There are, however, many challenges in empowering the youth to improve their skills and to retain or mobilize them toward agriculture sector. Creating interest and building confidence among youth towards agriculture is difficult but not impossible. As there is a lot of evidence available about profitable venture under diverse situation in agriculture sector. An assessment is needed to identify the vulnerable sections of the rural areas that have mindset of migrating from the farm sector to the non-farm sector. The main cause need to be analysed and necessary measures should be taken to change the mind set of the young generation. Generating employment to the rural people and generating regular income in agriculture and allied sector is the most important. Many a times, traditional form of agriculture divert the interest of the younger section from farming to non farm activities. Modern technology and skill intensive farming can attract in large proportion of the rural youth can bring to the livelihood. In the present scenario , agriculture sector should focus on market driven system where farmers can get higher return on their products with quality..

Farm youth are the precious human assets who can play an important role in the developmental activities as well as in agriculture because of their family and community background in agriculture and allied activities. If the talents and abilities of farm youth are properly nurtured and systematically guided, agriculture can attain sustained growth and bring prosperity to the country. Engaging youth in agriculture has been a prominent topic recently and has risen up the development agenda, as there is growing concern worldwide that young people have become disenchanted with agriculture. It is vital that young people are connected with farming since 85 per cent of the young people in the developing countries are depending on agriculture for their livelihood. In this backdrop, the present study is carried out with the following specific objectives

Objectives:

1. To analyze the perception of farm youth towards agriculture.
2. To find out the relationship between personal, socio-economic, psychological and communication characteristics of farm youth with their perception towards agriculture
3. To enlist the problems and suggestions of farm youth practicing agriculture

METHODOLOGY

The present study was carried out in Samagur, Rupahi, Laekhowa and Kalianbor Dev. blocks of Nagaon district in Assam state during 2023-24. Nagaon district was purposively selected for the study since this district is one of the leading agriculturally progress district . Moreover the researcher is familiar with the study area. From each of the sampled blocks , five villages were randomly selected for the study. In each village, ten farm youth practicing agriculture were again randomly selected for the study. Thus the total sample constitutes 200 farm youth from 20 villages of four blocks in Nagaon district. Data was collected using a pre-tested interview schedule. Ex-post facto research design was employed for the study.

Perception of farm youth towards agriculture :

Perception of farm youth towards agriculture is operationally defined in the present study as the interpretation of farm youth about agricultural practices. A scale on perception towards agriculture was developed for the study which was found to be reliable and valid. The perception

scale consisted of 18 statements and the responses were obtained on a five point continuum of agreement representing 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree' and 'strongly disagree' assigning a weightage of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The perception score of a respondent was calculated by adding up the scores obtained by him / her on all 18 items/statements. The perception score of this scale ranges from a minimum of 18 to a maximum of 90. Higher score on this scale indicates that the respondent has higher level of perception towards agriculture. Information regarding 19 personal, socioeconomic, psychological and communication characteristics (independent variables) of farm youth were collected using a structured schedule with suitable scales. The collected data was scored, tabulated and analyzed using frequency, mean, percentage, zero order correlation test and multiple regression analysis.

Results and discussions

Overall perception of farm youth towards agriculture :

It is observed from Table I that a slightly more than half (50.50%) of the farm youth had medium level of perception towards agriculture, whereas 26.00 and 23.50 per cent of the farm youth had high and low level of perception towards agriculture, respectively. It can be inferred that as high as 76.50 per cent of the farm youth had medium to high level of perception towards agriculture.

TABLE I Overall perception of farm youth towards agriculture

Perception	Number	Percent
Low	47	23.50
Medium	101	50.50
High	52	26.00
Total	200	100.00

Availability of improved agricultural technologies, employment throughout the year in farm activities, regular and decent income from agriculture, accessibility of gross root extension functionaries and adequate opportunities to participate in extension activities are reasons for over three fourth (76.50%) of the farm youth having medium to high level of perception towards agriculture. The present findings are in line with the findings of the study conducted by

Wachenheim and Rathge (2000); Ahmed et al. (2004); Sosuedward (2004); Olaniyi et al.(2011) and Josefina et al. (2012). Statement-wise perception of farm youth towards agriculture : Table II presents the data on the statement-wise perception of farm youth towards agriculture. With respect to the economic dimension, a greater number of the farm youth had ‘strongly agreed’ for the statements such as: (a) there is scope for upgrading livelihood in agriculture (32%), (b) practicing agriculture leads to economic up-liftment of farmers (30%) and (c) there is enough opportunity for career development in agriculture (29%). Most of the farm youth had ‘agreed’ for the statements like : (a) agriculture is a profitable venture (35%), (b) agriculture sector has more influence on the overall development of community (31%), (c) good number of farm youth programs supports youth to take up agriculture as a career (28%), and (d) greater economic prosperity could be achieved in agriculture (26%). In the respect of technical dimension, a larger number of farm youth had ‘strongly agreed’ for the statements such as: (a) promoting advanced scientific agriculture do help for farmers prosperity (32%), and (b) agriculture is a scientific activity (27%). More number of farm youth had ‘agreed’ for the statements like: (a) employment status could be improved by opting modern agriculture practices (30%), (b) timely operation and required agricultural inputs usage leads to optimum output (29%), (c) appropriate skill training will improve the participation of farm youth in agriculture (29%), and (d) scope for agricultural growth has to be enlarged in terms of agro-based activities (28%).

TABLE II: Perception of farm youth towards agriculture

Statement	SA	A	UD	DA	SDA
1.Economic Dimension					
A. Agriculture is a profitable venture	58 (29)	70 (35)	28 (14)	24 (12)	20 (10)
B. Agriculture sector has more influence on theover all development of community.	60 (30)	62 (31)	22 (11)	26 (13)	30 (15)
C. There is scope for upgrading livelihood in agriculture	64 (32)	58 (29)	26 (13)	28 (14)	24 (12)
D. Practicing agriculture leads to economic up- liftment of farmers	60 (30)	40 (20)	52 (26)	24 (12)	24 (12)
E. There is enough opportunity for career development in agriculture	58 (29)	50 (25)	34 (17)	30 (15)	28 (14)
F. Greater economic prosperity could be achieved in	50 (25)	52 (26)	36 (18)	32 (16)	30 (15)

agriculture	40 (20)	56 (28)	38 (19)		
G. Good number of farm youth programs supports youth to take up agriculture as a career				34 (17)	32 (16)
II. Technology Dimension					
A. Timely operation and required agricultural inputs usage leads to optimum output	44 (22)	58 (29)	22 (11)	36 (18)	40(20)
B. Promoting advanced scientific agriculture do help for farmers prosperity	64 (32)	42 (21)	26 (13)	34 (17)	34 (17)
C. Scope for agricultural growth has to be enlarged in terms of agro-based activities	52 (26)	56 (28)	20 (10)	32 (16)	40 (20)
D. Employment status could be improved by opting modern agriculture practices	42 (21)	60 (30)	30 (15)	34 (17)	16 (8)
E. Agriculture is a scientific activity	54 (27)	40 (20)	32 (16)	40 (20)	34 (17)
F. Appropriate skill training will improve the participation of farm youth in agriculture	42 (21)	58 (29)	18 (9)	42 (21)	40 (20)
III Other Dimension					
A. Practicing farming facilitate food security	40 (20)	64 (32)	24 (12)	36 (18)	36 (18)
B. Water resource is essential for enhancing farm productivity	66 (33)	34 (17)	30 (15)	36 (18)	34 (17)
C. I am proud of being a member of an agricultural family	20(10)	54(27)	46 (23)	48 (24)	32 (16)
D. Persons with passion towards agriculture can only practice farming	42 (21)	56 (28)	34 (17)	34 (17)	34 (17)
E. Agriculture guarantees physical health and mental peace	38 (19)	60 (30)	30 (15)	32 (16)	36 (18)

SA = Strongly agree; A= Agree; U= Undecided; D=Disagree; SDA= Strongly Disagree; Figure in parenthesis indicates percentage

With regard to the other dimensions, nearly one-third of the farm youth had ‘strongly agreed’ for the statement: ‘water resource is essential for enhancing farm productivity’(33%). Whereas, more number of farm youth had ‘agreed’ for the statements such as: (a) practicing farming facilitate food security (32%), (b) agriculture guarantees physical health and mental peace (30%), (c) persons with passion towards agriculture can only practice farming (28%), and (d) I am proud

of being a member of an agricultural family (27%). It can be referred that most of the farm youth had 'agreed' for all the statements measuring the perception towards agriculture.

The findings denotes that the farm youth have better perception towards agriculture. Relationship between personal, socioeconomic, psychological and communication characteristics of farm youth with their perception towards agriculture : The relationship between personal, socio-economic, psychological and communication characteristics of farm youth with their perception towards agriculture independent variables is presented in Table III. It could be observed from the results that 15 out of 19 independent variables were found to have significant to highly significant relationship with the perception of farm youth towards agriculture. Education, family size, land holding, family income, risk orientation, economic motivation, innovative proneness, social participation, mass media use, extension contact, extension participation, cosmopolitaness and farm scientist contact of farm youth had positive and highly significant relationship with perception towards agriculture at one per cent level. Similarly, farming commitment and training received of farm youth had positive and significant relationship with perception towards agriculture at five per cent level. The remaining variables such as, marital status, family type, farming experience and leisure time activities of farm youth had non-significant relationship with the perception towards agriculture. For every unit increase in the education, family size, l and holding, family income, risk orientation, economic motivation, innovative proneness, social participation, mass media use, extension contact, extension participation, cosmopolitaness, farm scientist contact. Farming commitment and training received of farm youth there will be an increase in the perception level. The contribution of 19 selected socio-economic, psychological and communication characteristics of farm youth towards perception was assessed and the findings are presented in Table III.

The findings revealed that nine out of 19 independent variables namely, land holding, family income, risk orientation, innovative proneness, farming commitment, social participation, mass media use, cosmo politeness and farm scientist contact of farm youth had contributed significantly towards developing perception of farm youth towards agriculture. The R2 value indicated that all the 19 independent variables had contributed to the tune of 70.50 per cent of variation in developing better perception of farm youth towards agriculture.

TABLE III

Relationship of personal, socio-economic, psychological and communication characteristics of farm youth with their perception towards agriculture (n = 200)

Sl No	Independent variables	Correlation coefficient 'r' value	Regression Coefficient	SE of regression coefficient	't' value
X1	Education	0.399 **	0.1016	0.3275	0.31 NS
X2	Marital status	-0.026 NS -	0.7586	0.8039	0.94 NS
X3	Family size	0.177**	-0.1740	0.4324	0.40 NS
X4	Type of family	0.047	-0.732	1.110	0.66 NS
X5	Farming experience	0.098 NS	0.0516	0.125	0.41 NS
X6	Land holdings	0.464 **	0.4379	0.1947	2.25 **
X7	Family income	0.228 **	0.0795	0.0403	1.97 *
X8	Risk orientation	0.375 **	0.9065	0.4050	2.24 **
X9	Economic motivation	0.195 **	-0.5775	0.4611	1.25 NS
X10	Innovative proneness	0.403 **	0.9941	0.2289	4.34 **
X11	Farming commitment	0.151 *	0.2276	0.0983	2.31 **
X12	Leisure time activities	0.072 NS	0.0453	0.1869	0.24 NS
X13	Social participation	0.474 **	0.1964	0.0626	3.14 **
X14	Mass media use	0.678 **	2.0201	0.2112	9.57 **
X15	Extension contact	0.337 **	0.0739	0.2020	0.37 NS
X16	Extension participation	0.290 **	0.0212	0.1276	0.17 NS
X17	Cosmopolitaness	0.352 **	0.1399	0.0475	2.94 **
X18	Training received	0.162 *	0.0909	0.9214	0.10 NS
X19	Farm scientist contact	0.394 **	0.0914	0.0462	1.98 *

NS =Non-Significant; * Significant at 5 % level; ** Significant at 1 % level ; R2 = 0.705; F= 21.31**

Problems and suggestions of farm youth practicing agriculture :

It can be observed from Table IV that lack of necessary timely inputs, lack of irrigation facilities, electricity problem, and scarcity of labor were the most important problems faced by the farm youth obtaining I, II, III and IV ranks, respectively. The other problems such as lack of transportation facility, lack of credit support, lack of storage facility and high cost of production and lower returns were placed in between V and VIII rank, respectively. Lack of training programmes, lack of proper guidance and fear of crop failure have obtained the last three ranks. The findings of the study are in line with findings of Prameelamma (1990) and Hadagali Vishwanath (2013).

TABLE IV

Problems and suggestions of farm youth practicing agriculture (n = 200)

Problems & Suggestion	Number	Per cent	Rank
A. Problems	182	91.0	I
Lack of necessary timely inputs like seeds and fertilizers			
Lack of Irrigation facilities	174	87.0	II
Electricity problem	162	81.0	III
Scarcity of labour	152	76.0	IV
Lack of transportation facility	144	72.0	V
Lack of credit support	136	68.0	VI
Lack of storage facility	128	64.0	VII
High cost of production and lower returns	122	61.0	VIII
Lack of training programmes	118	59.0	IX
Lack of proper guidance	104	52.0	X
Fear of crop failure	49	25	XI
B. suggestion			
Providing irrigation facility 176 88.0 I	176	88.0	I
Regular supply of power 168 84.0 II	168	84.0	II

Timely supply of necessary inputs (seeds/ planting material)	158	79.0	III
Timely provision of subsidy/credit (financial support)	142	71,0	IV
Conducting educational activities to create awareness among farm youth	136	68.0	V
Provide training programme	124	62.0	VI
Establishment of local market	118	59.0	VII
Establishment of local market	118	59	VIII

Table IV also reveals that provision of irrigation facility, supply of regular power, timely supply of necessary inputs and timely provision of credit were accorded the first four ranks with respect to the suggestions offered by farm youths to overcome the problems. Conducting educational activities to create awareness among farm youth, providing training programme, establishment of local market and establishment of storage facility were accorded V, VI, VII and VIII ranks, respectively in respect of suggestions to overcome the problems. The research results revealed that as high as 76.50 per cent of the farm youth had medium to high level of perception towards agriculture. There is need to improve the perception of farm youth towards agriculture by providing adequate facilities (irrigation, agricultural inputs, technical guidance, market for the produce at village level etc.) by the government agencies to carry out farming more effectively. The information on latest technologies needs to be provided to the farm youth through well organized educational programmes (discussion meetings, demonstrations, video conference, field days, krishi mela, exhibitions, campaign etc.) by Agricultural Universities, Line Departments and other concerned agencies. It is also necessary to promote young farmers commodity based associations wherever necessary to mainstream the youth into development process.

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